

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

USING CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

This article discusses the importance of using cloud technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language. It studied the concept and role of cloud technologies in modern language education. An analysis was also carried out to determine the effectiveness of using cloud technologies in interdisciplinary English language teaching.

Keywords: foreign language, cloud technologies, technology, educational process, teaching.

Nowadays, information technology has firmly entered the educational walls. Modern education can no longer function successfully in the old pedagogical forms. This means that the new school, the education system necessarily requires the use of new technologies, not only pedagogical, but also computer. One of the promising areas of development of modern information technologies is cloud technologies. Cloud technologies are a new digital model, the essence of which is to allow creating and storing applications for users, in our case for teachers and students. With the help of cloud technologies, all data and educational materials are placed on the Internet and are available to teachers and students, providing individuality and mobility in the use of resources for teaching and learning, facilitating collaboration, communication and sharing of resources, as well as the implementation of individual training. The following authors are devoted to the topic of cloud technologies in education: Gordyushin A.V., Lebedeva S.V., Shekerbekova Sh.T., Sukhanova N.T., Tarasov V.A., Kovalenko M.I., Sobol B.V. Stupina M.V., Vergasova O.M., Konishchev A.S., Skleiter N., Akkerman T., Itinson K. S. Batishchev A.V., Riz J., Dukkardt A.N., Sudarkina E.S., Panasenko E.A., Vorontsov A.A., Martyshkin A.I., Markin E.I., Nesipkaliev U., Adkins S., Belamarik J., Girsh V., Neil Skleiter and others [1].

In the educational process, "cloud technologies" began to develop and be applied in foreign countries since 2008. In our country, cloud services were used in the information and educational environment of an educational institution mainly as hosting free mail services, other cloud technology capabilities were practically not used. This was due to the lack of sufficient information and specialists with practical skills to introduce them into the educational process. Active improvement of hardware, especially processor power, multi-core architecture, disk volume and Internet channel speed, has allowed cloud technologies to develop. The "cloud" is considered not as the Internet itself, but as a set of hardware and software tools that provide processing and execution of client requests [2].

In the modern world, information technologies in the field of education are a necessary condition for the

progressive development of society. The improvement and computerization of educational process technologies is one of the main among the many new directions of education development. The importance of using cloud technologies in education lies in the fact that they not only serve as tools, but also provide qualitatively new learning opportunities, the formation of independent learning skills and contribute to the creation of new forms of learning.

Cloud technologies allow teachers and students to create and store educational information assets in online information repositories and have a number of advantages:

- mobility - you can work not only directly in the classroom, but also in any place where there is Internet access;
- the ability to use the latest versions of programs and at the same time do not need to monitor the release of updates;
- cost-effectiveness - there is no need to purchase licensed software, in addition, it does not matter in which operating system a particular user prefers to work - web services work in the browser of any OS;
- the ability to collaborate with other users on the same document or project;
- access to secure storage at any time from any device with internet access (personal computers, tablets, laptops, phones, etc.) [3].

The directions of using cloud technologies in educational activities include:

1. Collaboration of employees on documents. For example, an educational program or an annual plan. This document is compiled by administration employees and teachers responsible for any direction, for example, a psychologist, a social pedagogue or a person responsible for health care. Everyone is responsible for their own part of the document and cannot make changes to other blocks. To collaborate in the cloud, you need to create or place a document in cloud storage and share it with everyone who has a link or email addresses.

2. Joint project work of students. Students are given topics for projects. Then they are divided into 2 groups. Each group has its own responsibilities. The supervisor creates the document and grants access. These can be links or email addresses. Students work on a project at home or at an educational institution, filling out documents with content. At the end of the work, the teacher is granted access. If necessary, the teacher leaves comments for correction by students. For example, using Google Docs, the main advantage of which is the possibility of joint editing of documents (texts, photos, presentations, tables).

3. Distance education. The teacher offers students a task using an electronic journal. For example, written assignments. The student either creates a document or works with it. The teacher can view the modified document because he has access to it. The introduction of cloud technologies is an irreversible process that goes on as usual. In the near future, "clouds" will become the same widespread technology in our and other countries.

Today, cloud technologies are something that everyone uses almost daily. The rapid spread of cloud technologies sets us the task of integrating cloud services into the system of an educational institution. Cloud technologies have broad prospects for application in the field of education, research and applied development, as well as for distance learning. The use of cloud technologies in the educational process allows you to open an educational space [4].

Today, the information and educational space of universities is analyzed in the context of electronic reflection on the Internet of various aspects of university activities. There are various plans for designing an electronic learning environment that take into account the interests of different groups of Internet users. From a socio-psychological point of view, the role of the electronic educational environment of universities in improving educational technologies, the emergence of new aspects of teachers' activities, conditions for students' self-realization is revealed.

In general, cloud technologies represent a new way of organizing the educational process and offer an alternative to traditional methods. In addition, there is the possibility of personal training, collective training and interactive classes. The use of cloud technologies in the learning process leads to the optimization of the educational and methodological activities of the parties, increasing the effectiveness of communication links, minimizing the costs of the educational institution [5]. The use of cloud services is of great importance when teaching a foreign language, as it combines text, sound, graphic illustrations, video images, animation and, thus, allows you to simultaneously submit linguistic, speech and extralinguistic information in different ways. The systematic use of cloud technologies in English classes helps to increase internal motivation to study the subject and study in general. The motivation of students to study increases, more comfortable conditions for it are created [6].

The use of these technologies contributes to the integration of educational institutions into the global

educational space, promotes the development of relations with foreign partners on an equal basis. This is important for all specialties and areas of training of technical, humanitarian and classical universities and marks the transition of the domestic education system to a new qualitative level. That is, we have long since moved from the post-industrial era to the information one. The essence of cloud technologies is to provide users with remote access to services, computing resources and applications (including operating systems and infrastructure) via the Internet. The development of this direction of hosting (Hosting is a service for placing client equipment on the provider's territory, ensuring its connection to high-speed communication channels) was caused by the need for software and digital services that could be managed from the inside, but which would be more economical and efficient. In other words, we, ordinary users, get an information space — a cloud in which we can create, store and process various documents [7].

A striking example of cloud technologies that can be implemented in teaching foreign languages are the services provided by the Internet giant Google: Google Docs (documents, tables, presentations, forms, diagrams, drawings), Google Calendar (an electronic calendar with large reminders of events), informing a group of people about upcoming events), Google Mail (email with an advanced interface), Google Translate (online translator into all languages of the world), Google Groups (a service offering almost unlimited collaboration on creating, editing and publishing documents), Google Talk (a web client that provides live communication on the Internet), Google Labs (incubator of ideas for new services), etc. [8].

The results of the interaction of the subjects of the pedagogical process of teaching a foreign language are: the possibility of organizing joint activities and interpersonal interaction of the subjects of the educational process using cloud technologies; the ability of students to take into account different opinions and make efforts to coordinate different positions. At the same time, it cannot be argued that cloud technologies are innovative technologies for teaching a foreign language, but they provide an additional tool for the subjects of the learning process, and also introduce the effect of novelty into modern pedagogical technologies [9].

In conclusion, I would like to emphasize that new opportunities for improving the educational process and the educational system as a whole are opened precisely with the use of information and computer technologies that are constantly being introduced into education and contribute to its rise to a new level. These technologies belong to the technologies of the 21st century, and practice shows that with the introduction of new information and communication technologies, the study of foreign languages is moving from the field of research to the field of education and is becoming more widespread [10].

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INTEGRATIVE PROCESS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE CULTURE TO SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract

This article discusses the relevance of the integrative model of teaching foreign language culture to primary school children. Where the role of integration in the process of teaching a foreign language was studied. Also, the issue of foreign language culture in the process of teaching a foreign language with the use of interdisciplinary integration is analyzed.

Keywords: integrative model, foreign language culture, primary school age, foreign language, education.

Today, teaching foreign language communication to younger schoolchildren is one of the most popular areas of modern foreign language education aimed at the comprehensive development of students' personality by means of a foreign language. Since a foreign language is one of the most universal subjects that can enrich primary education, since children of primary school age have an innate and not yet lost ability to master languages, and languages, in turn, can become an effective means of children's development [1]. The activity-based nature of this educational subject, its versatility allow us to build the process of teaching a foreign language in a variety of content and organizational forms and understand it as a means of storing and transmitting various special knowledge, not just language. Within the framework of a positive assessment of the use of interdisciplinary connections in primary school and the undoubted advantages of a foreign language for younger schoolchildren, as well as its ability to integrate with other academic subjects, a prerequisite for building a foreign language course in primary school based on an integrative model [2].

In the modern theory and methodology of teaching foreign languages and the formation of the personality of a younger student, the expediency of using an integrative approach, which contains a huge potential, is emphasized. Therefore, the main advantage of

integration in teaching foreign languages to younger schoolchildren is the creation of conditions for the formation of a child's personality with a broad ideological mindset, capable of actively acting in various fields of activity in solving educational tasks of various directions. Integration makes it possible to improve the quality of knowledge acquisition by students due to the interpenetration of the content of different subjects and consideration of the same subject of study from the point of view of different subjects [3].

A foreign language as a subject creates all the conditions for the effective implementation of the integration model – the knowledge gained in the native language allows you to study a foreign language from different sides. Since it is a foreign language compatible with a large number of subjects, such as the world around us, the history of the country of the language being studied, fine arts, Kazakh/Russian language, literature, mathematics, music, technology in elementary school. Integrated lessons refer to non-standard forms of lessons. They are held rarely, once a quarter, six months or a year. they require the training and creative initiative of a group of teachers of various subjects. A foreign language is a special subject, but it is impossible to cover the full depth and complexity of linguistic phenomena without taking into account their psychological and social aspects [4].